

Sustainable Optimization of Petrochemical Supply Chains: A Simulation-Based Approach

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Abstract

The dual challenge of maximizing profits while minimizing environmental impact is a critical issue in modern petrochemical supply chains. This paper presents a simulation-based optimization model utilizing Discrete Event Simulation (DES) with ARENA software to improve the multi-echelon petrochemical supply chain, focusing specifically on reducing flare-related emissions and optimizing capacity constraints. Grounded in a real-world case from Saudi Arabia, this study aims to adjust operational strategies and capacity limits related to flaring to enhance efficiency and profitability while mitigating environmental harm. Comparative results reveal a 2.99% increase in profit and a 0.428% reduction in emissions, largely attributed to optimized flare management. These findings underscore the potential for significant sustainable improvements in petrochemical supply chain operations, providing actionable insights for balancing economic goals with environmental stewardship.

Keywords: Sustainable Petrochemical Supply Chain, Discrete Event Simulation, Emission Reduction.

1. Introduction

Overseeing the petrochemical supply chain (PSC) entails addressing multiple challenges, such as optimizing production planning, managing inventories, coordinating reverse logistics, and mitigating environmental impacts. Achieving efficient production and distribution of chemical products demands a careful balance between maintaining production capacity, ensuring quality, and adapting to dynamic market needs. The process is further complicated by the intricate interconnections between various products and processes. [1, 2].

Effective inventory management in the PSC is crucial to maintaining a steady supply of raw materials and finished goods, ensuring uninterrupted production processes. This task becomes even more challenging with the need to handle hazardous substances and cut down environmental emissions, particularly through flaring reduction. Adopting streamlined production and inventory strategies is vital not only for economic viability but also for lessening the industry's ecological impact. This is particularly relevant in Saudi Arabia, where the petrochemical industry, heavily reliant on hydrocarbons, contributes approximately 77% of export revenue and 42% of GDP, highlighting the importance of robust supply chain management [3]. This holds particular importance in Saudi Arabia, where the petrochemical industry, predominantly dependent on hydrocarbons, accounts for roughly 77% of the country's export revenues and 42% of its GDP, emphasizing the essential role of efficient supply chain management [13, 14].

Table 9. Review of Research on Petrochemical Supply Chain Simulations (a).

Ref	Type of Hydrocarbon (C1-C5)	Main Product	Segment			Decision levels		Uncertain Parameters			Environmental Aspects	Simulation Tools
			US	MS	DS	S	T	S	P	Y		
[4]	C1	Methanol	✓			✓	✓		✓	✓	✓	Aspen
[5]	C1	Methanol, Transportation fuels, Ethylene, Propylene, Butadiene		✓	✓	✓	✓					
[6]	-	C1 (Shale Gas)	✓				✓	✓	✓		✓	Lingo
[7]	C4, C5+	Ethylene, Butenes, Butadiene	✓				✓	✓			✓	Spyro
[8]	C2	Butadiene	✓			✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	Aspen
[9]	C2, C5+	Butadiene, Butenes, Ethylene, Propylene, Acetaldehyde, Hydrogen	✓			✓			✓	✓	✓	SimaPro
[10]	-	Petroleum	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	
[11]	-	Oil, Water	✓			✓	✓		✓		✓	VFPi and MATLAB
[12]	C1 - C5+	Ethane, Propane, Ethylene, Naphtha, Benzene, Ammonia, Urea, Methanol	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓		✓	GAMS
[12]	C3, C4	C3, C4	✓	✓		✓	✓		✓		✓	CPLEX 12.3.
This Study	C2 - C5+	Butadiene, 1-Butene	✓				✓	✓			✓	Arena

Table 1. Review of Research on Petrochemical Supply Chain Simulations (b).

Ref	Type of Hydrocarbon (C1-C5)	Main Product	Modeling Approaches										
			LP	MILP	NLP	MINLP	DP	SP	SO	MO	CM	PM	RM
[4]	C1	Methanol	✓						✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
[5]	C1	Methanol, Transportation fuels, Ethylene, Propylene, Butadiene											
[6]	-	C1 (Shale Gas)				✓					✓	✓	✓
[7]	C4, C5+	Ethylene, Propylene, Butenes, Butadiene	✓						✓				
[8]	C2	Butadiene	✓		✓				✓		✓		✓
[9]	C2, C5+	Butadiene, Butenes, Ethylene, Propylene, Acetaldehyde, Hydrogen			✓				✓		✓		✓
[10]	-	Petroleum	✓						✓	✓		✓	
[11]	-	Oil, Water			✓	✓		✓		✓			
[12]	C1 - C5+	Ethane, Propane, Ethylene, Naphtha, Benzene, Ammonia, Urea, Methanol		✓				✓		✓			✓
[12]	C3, C4	C3, C4		✓				✓		✓		✓	
This Study	C2 - C5+	Butadiene, 1-Butene	✓						✓	✓		✓	✓

Managing the return and reuse of materials through reverse logistics introduces significant challenges, as it must comply with stringent regulations and address the complexities of hazardous waste management [5, 15, 16]. Additionally, achieving a lower environmental impact demands a strong focus on adopting green technologies and comprehensive approaches to sustainability

The unpredictable nature of production efficiency and material quality significantly influences the dynamics of supply chains, affecting operational efficiency, product consistency, and waste management processes in the petrochemical sector [17, 18]. In such cases, simulation-based optimization serves as a vital strategy. This approach enables decision-makers to evaluate multiple scenarios systematically, examining the outcomes across different production and material conditions. This detailed analysis helps to identify effective strategies for maintaining supply stability, improving

productivity, and promoting environmental responsibility, ultimately supporting precise adjustments to enhance operational efficiency.

This research targets the optimization of production and inventory systems in the C4 supply chain of Saudi Arabia's hydrocarbon sector. The objective is to increase profitability while reducing supply shortages and flaring events. Using advanced simulation platforms like Arena, the study develops approaches to improve the performance of three crucial components: raw material suppliers, intermediate production stages, and end-user distribution, ultimately boosting both operational efficiency and financial outcomes.

2. Overview of Simulation Methods and Tools in Literature

The literature reviewed for this research is outlined in **Error! Reference source not found.**, categorizing studies based on variables such as the hydrocarbon type, primary product, operational segment, decision-making level, modeling techniques, uncertain factors, environmental considerations, and the simulation software utilized. This research specifically targets two key products, Butadiene and Butene-1, which rely on C2, C3, and NGL as inputs. **Error! Reference source not found.** highlights the allocation of research publications concerning the simulation tools employed and their associated methodologies.

Table 10. Overview of Simulation Methods and Tools in Literature [19].

No.	Tool	DES	ABS	Hybrid	NA	Total
1	AnyLogic	3	2	1		6
2	Arena	30				30
3	AutoMod	1				1
4	ExtendSim	5				5
5	GBSE	1				1
6	GPSS	1				1
7	HERMES	3				3
8	Jadex		1			1
9	LogiRisk	1				1
10	NetLogo		2	1		3
11	OTD-NET	1				1
12	PlantSimulation	2				2
13	ProModel	3				3
14	Repast		4			4
15	Simio	4				4
16	Simul8	3				3
17	BaseStockSim	1				1
18	software	1	1		2	4
19	Swarm		2			2
20	Witness	1				1
21	Not specified	8	7	1		16
Total		69	19	3	2	93

Among 93 reviewed scholarly articles, the prevalent methodology identified is Discrete Event Simulation (DES), which has been exclusively utilized in 69 studies [19]. A significant factor contributing to this dominance is the frequent use of Arena simulation software, highlighted in 30

articles, as it primarily supports DES. Arena's strong presence in the literature underscores its advanced technological features and its relevance to the evolving demands of simulation-based research.

2.1. An Overview of the Petrochemical SC

In Fig. 4, the complexities of optimizing production and inventory management within the C4 supply chain are highlighted, where the goal is to meet demand while ensuring maximum profitability. Coordination is required across three key levels: feedstock suppliers, intermediate processes such as the Butene-1 unit and Butadiene plant, and the final customers. To achieve profitability, challenges like managing supply shortages, reducing flaring in the Sphere, controlling fixed feedstock expenses, and maintaining a 10% safety stock in tanks and the Sphere must be addressed. Leveraging simulation tools like Arena software becomes essential for navigating these complexities, enabling strategic solutions to improve outcomes in the hydrocarbon market. The conceptual model further elaborates on these aspects.

Fig. 4. Illustration of the Petrochemical Supply Chain.

3. Methodology

Establishing a clear and structured methodology is crucial before starting the analysis. This ensures a systematic approach to building the model and conducting the simulation study. The upcoming section details the primary steps necessary for executing the simulation process.

This study seeks to optimize profitability inside the petrochemical supply chain system by adhering to the subsequent measures.

1. Gathering Data

Gathering all pertinent information forms the basis of the simulation, which involves obtaining data on key variables like production rates, capacity, supply, and demand.

2. Construct a Conceptual Framework

The simulation model is constructed based on the conceptual framework, integrating the data gathered in step 2 to establish parameters and variables. The conceptual model applied in this case study is depicted in Fig. 5.

3. Develop the Simulation Model

Building upon the conceptual model's framework, the simulation model is created using ARENA software. This step involves coding and setting up the software to mirror the structure and behavior outlined in the conceptual model. Additionally, it requires integrating the data collected in step 2 to establish parameters and variables.

4. Verify and validate the model

This crucial step involves verifying the simulation model to ensure it is free from errors. Verification is typically accomplished by comparing the simulation outputs with expected results under predefined conditions. Subsequently, the model's performance is validated by comparing its results with the actual system's performance, often with input from managers.

5. Optimization

Execute the simulation model across a range of scenarios to analyze the system's potential outcomes and behavior. These scenarios involve modifying input parameters to represent different conditions, such as increasing or decreasing control variables, to identify the system's optimal configuration. This process is supported by tools such as OptQuest.

3.1. Model Development

PSC Conceptual Framework. Arena software, extensively used for discrete event simulation (DES) across numerous industries, is celebrated for its ability to simulate complex systems, streamline operations, and enable data-driven decision-making. Scenarios can be tested, inefficiencies identified, and processes optimized to address challenges proactively before real-world implementation. Its strong visualization features aid in comprehending and communicating intricate system dynamics, while its flexibility and customization options make it applicable to a wide range of areas, including industrial supply chains and multi-echelon systems. This section provides an in-depth exploration of the conceptual framework and design of the petrochemical supply chain, thoroughly examining its processes and components.

Fig. 5 presents the conceptual framework for the supply chain processes in the system. The process starts with sourcing critical raw materials, such as ethane, ethylene (C2), propane, propylene (C3), and natural gas liquids (NGL) with C5+ components, from various suppliers. These materials are the primary inputs for Olefin plant crackers, which are essential in generating C4 compounds like butane-1, butane-2, butadiene (1-3), isobutane, and isobutene. The crackers operate by heating saturated hydrocarbons to temperatures above 850°C, causing molecular bonds to break and smaller molecules to form. In this system, ethane, ethylene (C2), and NGL with C5+ components are processed in OLF-2, while propane and propylene (C3) are sent to OLF-3.

In this process, a portion of the C4 output from OLF-2 is stored in the Sphere, whereas part of the production from OLF-3 is sent to a storage tank. After the crackers generate C4 compounds, they are transferred to the Butadiene and Butene-1 plants. If the supply from OLF-2 and OLF-3 is insufficient to meet the demands of both plants, additional C4 is sourced externally. Within the Butene-1 unit, two outputs are produced: RAF-1, delivered to customer 2, and RAF-3, provided to customer 1. Some of the RAF-3 is also stored in the Sphere. 'Raffinate' (RAFF) refers to the product left after certain components are removed, while the separated materials are known as the extract.

Fig. 2. The conceptual framework (b).

Fig. 2. The conceptual framework (c).

Develop the Simulation Model on Arena. The simulation model is constructed using the conceptual framework of the petrochemical supply chain, emphasizing factors such as sphere capacity, tank capacity, and the operational dynamics of the butadiene and butene plants. A material balance approach is applied, with a uniform distribution between 26% and 47% to simulate butadiene percentage data [20]. The development process begins with systematically identifying the core components and processes of the supply chain, including raw material inputs, production phases, storage facilities, and distribution pathways. Once these elements are defined, input data such as processing durations, storage limits, and transportation timelines are input into Arena to ensure the

system is accurately modeled. This structured methodology guarantees that the simulation model is comprehensive and reliable.

4. Result and Discussion

4.1. Verification and validation

To verify the model's accuracy, it was animated, allowing the tracking of material flow and various performance measures. The results confirm that the inflow at each production or storage stage matches the outflow of that stage. The data was cross-checked with the values in Table 11 and Table 12 to ensure the correctness of the input and output values.

Based on this information, one ton of C4 in the BTD plant will produce Raffinates (42% C4), Acetylenes (5% C4), Butadiene (approximately between 26-47%), with the remaining portion classified as off-spec. For instance, Raffinate represents 42% of 37 tons, which equals 15.54 tons. This section will outline the methods used to verify the simulation model, including a comparison of manual calculations with the system's outputs to ensure the accuracy of the model.

In another plant, a ton of a mixture containing 60% C4 and 40% Raff in a BTN unit will produce Butene-1 (50% of the mixture), Raff-3 (20% of the mixture), and Raff-1 (30% of the mixture). By manually calculating these percentages and comparing them with the system's outputs, the material balances are confirmed to be correct. This detailed modeling approach allows for testing various scenarios, optimizing operations, and making informed decisions that enhance overall supply chain performance. The following tables provide further details:

Table 11. Review of certain numerical inputs in the existing system.

Location	Input	Average (Ton/Hour)
Butene-1 Unit	C4 and Raffinate	17.1262
Butadiene Plant	C4	37.0002

Table 12. Review of certain numerical outputs in the existing system.

Location	Output	Average (Ton/Hour)
Butadiene Plant	Butadiene	13.4964
	Raff	15.5401
	ACE	1.8500
	Offspec	6.1137
Butene-1 Unit	Butene-1	8.5631
	Raff-3	3.4252
	Raff-1	5.1378

By comparing the manual calculations with the system's outputs, we ensure that the material balances are accurately represented. This validation step is essential for maintaining the integrity of the simulation model and ensuring the reliability of the results. The following section will explore the optimal solutions, achieved by adjusting control variables to maximize profit while accounting for flare amount.

4.2. Optimization

To align with the material balance constraints and the objectives of profit maximization, shortage prevention, and flare reduction, efforts are concentrated on regulating the minimum recycle performance, the flaring limit of the Sphere, and the supply quantities, as detailed in Table 13. The system’s potential behavior and outcomes are evaluated by running the simulation model across three different scenarios. For optimization purposes, the OptQuest tool is utilized during the simulation process.

Table 13. Feasible Values of Decision Variables.

No	Decision Variables	Minimum	Suggested	Maximum	Step
1	C2 supply (in MMCSF)	3	7	11	0.40
2	C3 supply (in MBD)	30	50	70	2.00
3	NGL supply (in MBD)	20	35	50	2.00
4	Minimum Recycle Quantity (in Ton/h)	3	11	19	0.80
5	Limit to Flare (in Ton)	1,539	2,916	3,159	81.00

The objective of this study is to prioritize environmental considerations, with a specific focus on reducing flare amounts, while also ensuring high profitability. According to the results from OptQuest, the optimal solution yields a profit of \$27,648.87 per hour, with a flare amount is 0.946 ton per hour. This solution was attained by adjusting the control variables: receiving C2 at 11 MMCSF, C3 at 60 MBD, and NGL at 50 MBD, the recycling rate to 19 tons/hour, and setting the flare limit to 2,616 tons.

Table 14. The Best Solution.

No	Profit (\$/hr)	Flare (Ton/hr)	C2 (MMCSF)	C3 (MBD)	NGL (MBD)	Recycle (Ton/hr)	Sphere's Limit (Ton)
1	27,648.87	0.946	11	60	50	19	2,616
2	27,641.17	0.943	11	60	50	19	2,916
3	27,630.84	0.942	11	60	50	19	2,766
4	27,614.04	0.944	11	60	50	19	3,216
5	27,606.46	0.944	11	60	50	19	3,066
6	27,445.61	0.943	11	60	45	19	2,766
7	27,443.98	0.942	11	60	45	19	2,616
8	27,433.02	0.943	11	60	45	19	2,916
9	27,432.92	0.941	11	60	45	19	3,216
10	27,426.02	0.942	11	60	45	19	3,066
11	27,318.80	0.942	11	60	40	19	2,616
12	27,318.46	0.940	11	60	40	19	2,766
13	27,304.40	0.941	11	60	40	19	3,216
14	27,068.13	0.947	11	65	50	19	2,616
15	27,027.11	0.945	11	65	50	19	2,916
16	27,008.02	0.944	11	65	50	19	3,216
17	27,004.53	0.945	11	65	50	19	3,066
18	26,934.33	0.944	10	60	50	19	2,616
19	26,926.82	0.946	10	60	50	19	2,766
20	26,922.66	0.943	10	60	50	19	3,066

Adjusting the flare limit requires careful consideration, as reducing it might lead to unintended consequences, such as more frequent flaring events, increased flaring expenses, and reduced profitability. Although a lower flare limit can provide extra storage capacity during flaring scenarios, it often results in less efficient operations and higher costs. Conversely, raising the flare limit could

- [6] Gholami, Z., Gholami, F., Tişler, Z., Vakili, M.: A Review on the Production of Light Olefins Using Steam Cracking of Hydrocarbons. *Energies*. 14, 8190 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.3390/en14238190>.
- [7] Rodgers, S., Meng, F., Poulston, S., Conradie, A., McKechnie, J.: Renewable butadiene: A case for hybrid processing via bio- and chemo-catalysis. *Journal of Cleaner Production*. 364, 1–12 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2022.132614>.
- [8] Cabrera Camacho, C.E., Villanueva Perales, A.L., Alonso-Fariñas, B., Vidal-Barrero, F., Ollero, P.: Assessing the economic and environmental sustainability of bio-olefins: The case of 1,3-butadiene production from bioethanol. *Journal of Cleaner Production*. 374, 1–12 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2022.133963>.
- [9] Oliveira, F., Grossmann, I.E., Hamacher, S.: Accelerating Benders stochastic decomposition for the optimization under uncertainty of the petroleum product supply chain. *Computers & Operations Research*. 49, 47–58 (2014). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cor.2014.03.021>.
- [10] Tavallali, M.S., Karimi, I.A., Halim, A., Baxendale, D., Teo, K.M.: Well Placement, Infrastructure Design, Facility Allocation, and Production Planning in Multireservoir Oil Fields with Surface Facility Networks. *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.* 53, 11033–11049 (2014). <https://doi.org/10.1021/ie403574e>.
- [11] Beiranvand, H., Ghazanfari, M., Sahebi, H., Pishvae, M.S.: A robust crude oil supply chain design under uncertain demand and market price: A case study. *Oil Gas Sci. Technol. – Rev. IFP Energies nouvelles*. 73, 66 (2018). <https://doi.org/10.2516/ogst/2018056>.
- [12] Fernandes, L.J., Relvas, S., Barbosa-Póvoa, A.P.: Collaborative Design and Tactical Planning of Downstream Petroleum Supply Chains. *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.* 53, 17155–17181 (2014). <https://doi.org/10.1021/ie500884k>.
- [13] Hasanov, F.J., Javid, M., Joutz, F.L.: Saudi Non-Oil Exports before and after COVID-19: Historical Impacts of Determinants and Scenario Analysis. *Sustainability*. 14, 2379 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14042379>.
- [14] Kamboj, P., Hejazi, M., Qiu, Y., Kyle, P., Iyer, G.: The path to 2060: Saudi Arabia’s long-term pathway for GHG emission reduction. *Energy Strategy Reviews*. 55, 101537 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.esr.2024.101537>.
- [15] Banguera, L., Sepulveda, J.M., Fuertes, G., Carrasco, R., Vargas, M.: Reverse and Inverse Logistics Models for Solid Waste Management. *SAJIE*. 28, (2017). <https://doi.org/10.7166/28-4-1701>.
- [16] Rong, Y., Shen, Z.-J.M., Snyder, L.V.: The impact of ordering behavior on order-quantity variability: a study of forward and reverse bullwhip effects. *Flex Serv Manuf J.* 20, 95–124 (2008). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10696-009-9054-3>.
- [17] Chatzioannou, K., Farr, W.M.: Inferring the maximum and minimum mass of merging neutron stars with gravitational waves. *Phys. Rev. D.* 102, 064063(1–8) (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevD.102.064063>.
- [18] Du, B., Pan, C., Zhang, W., Chen, M.: Distributed Energy-Efficient Power Optimization for CoMP Systems With Max-Min Fairness. *IEEE Commun. Lett.* 18, 999–1002 (2014). <https://doi.org/10.1109/LCOMM.2014.2317734>.
- [19] Vieira, A.A.C., Dias, L.M.S., Santos, M.Y., Pereira, G.A.B., Oliveira, J.A.: Supply chain data integration: A literature review. *Journal of Industrial Information Integration*. 19, 1–15 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jii.2020.100161>.
- [20] Weissermel, K., Arpe, H.-J.: *Industrial organic chemistry*. VCH, Weinheim ; New York (1997).

Nomenclature and Abbreviation.

ACE	: Acetylenes	MTBE	: Methyl Tert-Butyl Ether
BTD	: Butadiene	NA	: Not Applicable
BTN	: Butene-1	Off-Spec	: Off-Specification
C2	: Ethane	OLF	: Olefins/Double bonds
C3	: Propane	PSC	: Petrochemical SC
C4	: Butane	SC	: Supply Chain
C5+ / NGL	: Natural Gas Liquid	Raff	: Raffinate
DES	: Discrete-Event Simulation	Raff-1	: Raffinate-1
MBD	: Thousand Barrels per day	Raff-2	: Raffinate-2
MMCSF	: Million Standard Cubic Feet	Raff-3	: Raffinate-3
		wt%	: weight (%)
